

EFFECTIVENESS OF DEVELOPING GAME ENDURANCE IN VOLLEYBALL FROM AN EARLY AGE

Allayarov Islambek Qasimjanovich

Nukus branch of the Uzbekistan State University of
Physical Education and Sport

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17033567>

In our republic, it is crucial to further increase the popularity of volleyball among the population, establish a system for selecting and training highly talented young volleyball players to the level of professional athletes, and elevate the country's volleyball to a level where it can compete equally with developed countries. Volleyball plays an important role in promoting a healthy lifestyle among the population by involving all segments of society in mass participation. Those who work from 9 a.m. to 6 p.m. can hardly find time for their personal life to engage in volleyball. However, morning exercises are very important for one's life. The benefit of morning exercises is that a person's energy level and motivation peak until 8 AM. If you use this time effectively for your body, it will soon provide an incentive to easily perform even the most difficult tasks. Simultaneously, scientific research was conducted on the study of young volleyball players and carrying out scientific and methodological research in preparation for competitions. In laboratory conditions, preliminary studies of the functional capabilities of volleyball players were conducted. According to anthropometric indicators, it was found that volleyball players Abdullayev Mardon, Ollomov Diyor, Nafasov Kamron, Fayziyev Shoxrux, Abduzoirov Nosirjon, and Mustafoqulov Ma'rufjon had lower body weight relative to their height, while volleyball players Yunusov Ulug'bek and Bozorov Faxriddin were found to have excess body weight. The remaining volleyball players were observed to be within normal range. It was observed that the remaining volleyball players were in normal condition.

At the beginning of the study, the anthropometric indicators of the volleyball players in the control group were determined and analyzed (see Table 1)

Table 1

N	Respondent's Full Name	Body length, (cm)	Weight (kg)	Chest circumference (at rest), cm	Chest circumference (inhalation), (cm)	Chest circumference (when exhaling), (cm)	Arm length (cm)	Leg length, (cm)	Forearm circumference, (cm)	Hip circumference, (cm)	Shoulder width (cm)
1	Amanbayev Serik	170	70	94	97	89,3	74	91	31	55	41
2	Xaitov Xurshid	180	79	95	97	93	74	106	32	58	40
3	Abdullayev Mardon	171	64	88	92	86	74	97	29	50	40
4	Kuziyev Toxir	165	65	74	88	82,7	74	94	30	55	38
5	Qo'chqorov Ziyodullo	176	75	100	104	98	77	101	36	57	43
6	Jabborov Lochinbek	162	62	89	92	87	74	90	33	53	41
7	Umirboyev Xursand	170	67	92	95,5	90	75	96	33	52	43
8	Fayziyev Shohrux	180	67	85	92	83	86	101	28	52	40
9	Ollomov Diyor	172	57	90	92	87	74	101	28	47	41
10	Norbobyev Sarvar	183	78	90	92	87	80	103	36	54	42
11	Topilbjonov Qahramon	169	69	92	95,5	90	77	95	33	53	41
12	Nafasov Kamron	168	52	95	97	93	68	90	36	50	40
13	Fayziyev Shaxzod	165	67	92	95,5	90	69	90	36	54	39
14	Ummatqulov Jahongir	172	70	85	92	83	71	93	34	54	41
15	Yunusov Ulug'bek	172	81	92	95,5	90	74	96	36	57	47
16	Bozorov Faxriddin	179	92	85	92	83	77	95	38	60	51
17	Mustafoqulov Ma'rufjon	172	57	90	92	87	80	103	36	54	42
18	Zaripov Olmosbek	189	88	89	92	87	83	110	35	59	45
19	Burxonov Jo'rabek	172	69	95	97	93	74	106	32	58	40
20	Abduzoirov Nosirjon	178	71	89	92	87	78	90	31	53	40

Additionally, the physical development indicators of the volleyball players in the control group were also determined and analyzed (see Table 2)

Table 2

Physical development indicators of volleyball players in the control group

No.	Respondent's full name	O2 (%) Before	Blood pressure SBP/DBP	Heart rate bpm before	Blood pressure SBP/DBP after	Heart rate bpm after	Running pace (s/km)	Recovery after 3 min of exercise	O2 (%) after
1	Amanbayev Serik	96	121/77	89	155/81	168	16	92	89
2	Xaitov Xurshid	97	130/89	101	163/93	168	14	106	94
3	Abdullayev Mardon	95	120/91	89	141/91	172	15	120	97
4	Kuziyev Toxir	97	106/76	90	149/90	172	16	112	94
5	Qo'chqorov Ziyodullo	98	165/76	90	139/80	160	14	123	84
6	Jabborov Lochinbek	97	120/83	88	131/77	174	17	123	94
7	Umirboyev Xursand	95	130/90	87	164/93	160	17	119	97
8	Fayziyev Shohrux	100	121/79	72	129/80	161	18	130	100
9	Ollomov Diyor	98	123/79	112	130/59	188	17	92	93
10	Norboboyev Sarvar	98	146/95	109	164/100	172	16	106	93
11	Topilbjonov Qahramon	95	130/83	94	125/89	181	14	123	93
12	Nafasov Kamron	82	125/70	91	120/90	183	15	119	79
13	Fayziyev Shaxzod	96	156/90	126	154/89	176	16	130	93
14	Ummatqulov Jahongir	93	128/97	106	150/76	188	14	92	91
15	Yunusov Ulug'bek	98	193/118	138	165/87	193	17	106	97
16	Bozorov Faxriddin	99	162/105	116.00	176/91	179.00	24	120	95
17	Mustafoqulov Marufjon	97	125/84	96	140/89	102	18	112	91
18	Zaripov Olmosbek	100	121/79	72	129/80	161	18	130	93
19	Burxonov Jo'rabek	98	123/79	112	130/59	188	17	92	91
20	Abduzoirov Nosirjon	98	146/95	109	164/100	172	16	106	97

This article is dedicated to studying the effectiveness of developing game endurance in volleyball players from an early age. According to the research results, the anthropometric indicators and levels of physical development of volleyball players were determined. It was found that some athletes (Abdullaev Mardon, Ollomov Diyor, Nafasov Kamron, Fayziev Shokhrux, Abduzoirov Nosirjon and Mustafokulov Marufjon) had below-normal body weight, while Yunusov Ulugbek and Bozorov Fakhrriddin were overweight. The remaining volleyball players fell within the normal range of indicators. Analysis of physical development indicators showed that the functional capabilities of volleyball players vary, and the recovery process after exercises and oxygen consumption have individual differences. These results emphasize

the importance of an individualized approach in training young volleyball players.

In conclusion, proper selection of volleyball players from an early age and constant monitoring of their physical and functional condition will enable us to elevate our country's volleyball to the level of developed nations.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people. - Tashkent: "O'zbekiston" NMIU, 2017, 48 p.
2. Platonov V.N. The System of Training Athletes in Olympic Sports. General theory and its practical applications. - Kiev: Olympic Literature, 2004, 808 p.
3. Pulatov A.A. Official Rules of Volleyball. Publishing and Printing Department of UzSIPC. -Tashkent, 2002, 53 pages.
4. Pulatov A.A. Volleyball. //Collection of lectures for first-year students of SIPC. -Tashkent, 2004, 71 pages.
5. Pulatov A.A., Isroilov Sh.Kh. Theory and Methodology of Volleyball. Textbook. - Tashkent, 2007, 148 pages.

